

INFINITE

BUILDINGRENOVATION

Industrialised envelope solutions

D7.10

Structuring the EU Observatory

Public Report

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Project information

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Coordinator

eurac
research

Project Partners

About the project

Offsite prefabrication of multifunctional envelopes has been shown to be a technically viable approach to increase rate and quality of deep renovation of residential buildings. However, several barriers are still preventing a massive adoption of prefabricated solutions.

INFINITE aims at boosting the building renovation sector through the so-called "**Renovation4.0**" approach, which leverages on both digitalisation and industrialisation to offer **tailor-made solutions** with a high level of **design freedom, decrease retrofit costs and time** thanks to the optimisation of the value-chain and **foster the adoption of eco-compatible long-lasting products** and systems.

To do so, the INFINITE Project relies on three main pillars:

1. cross-fertilisation from digitalisation trends in other markets (i.e. Industry4.0),
2. exploitation of industrial capabilities and coupling with LC-thinking approach
3. experience gained from the 1st generation of multifunctional prefabricated envelopes

INFINITE promotes a life cycle approach that allows for comprehensive design, optimisation of the O&M and depletion of end-of-life residual value.

INFINITE partners cover the whole renovation value-chain. Together, they will develop a new generation of residential building renovation products and actions centred on the all-in-one industrialised Life-Cycle-based approach. Expected outputs include:

- a set of multi-user and **multidisciplinary design tools**,
- **process-optimised all-in-one industrialised eco envelope kits**,
- **adaptive control systems**,
- set of **demand- and industry-side matched business models** to show the Renovation4.0 market potential,
- a **structured framework of entities and knowledge** able to clearly and widely demonstrate the Renovation4.0 benefits.

INFINITE will unleash the potential of the renovation industry by increasing the market penetration of sustainable, high-quality and long-lasting building retrofitting products and methods. This will ultimately contribute to the decarbonisation of the European building stock.

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Executive Summary

The Industrialized Deep Retrofit (IDR) Observatory is a central initiative within the H2020 INFINITE project. It is coordinated by EDERA to **establish a structured, stakeholder-driven knowledge and engagement platform**.

The Observatory is designed to serve **three main functions**:

- monitoring the evolution of IDR across Europe and globally
- enabling consistent and comparable data collection
- facilitating engagement among stakeholders in the IDR ecosystem.

Through **collaborative outreach**, including workshops and signed Letters of Support, EDERA has laid the groundwork for a neutral, evidence-based forum to promote consensus around the Renovation4.0 approach.

This **report** outlines the framework definition, the stakeholder engagement process, and early contributions of the Observatory to the bi-annual IDR outlooks, market activation and overall project dissemination.

1. Definition of the IDR Observatory

The EU Observatory for Industrialized Deep Renovation (IDR) is envisioned as a **dynamic, neutral infrastructure** to support the wide adoption of offsite retrofit approaches in Europe. It is intended to be an **open network** of entities interested in sharing best practices, as well as the vision of an intense market penetration of Renovation4.0. Such network is based on a **pool of EU experts** already active in the field of innovative renovation, willing to gather in an open innovation hub built around three core pillars that define the IDR Observatory as:

- **a system to observe the evolution of IDR at European and global scale**
The Observatory monitors IDR trends, innovations, policies, and performance outcomes. This includes tracking adoption rates, technological advancements, and policy impacts, offering a cross-national perspective on progress toward decarbonization goals in the built environment.
- **a framework to collect relevant and comparable data**
To enable evidence-based decisions, the Observatory facilitates structured data gathering from pilot projects, market studies, and case histories. Data includes technical specifications, energy performance indicators, cost-efficiency metrics, and socio-economic outcomes.
- **a platform to interact with the international IDR community**
The Observatory also acts as a participatory platform where stakeholders—researchers, public bodies, housing associations, and policy experts—exchange insights and experiences. This fosters cross-border learning and builds trust in the Renovation4.0 paradigm.

The structure of Observatory is meant to be very light and **synergic with existing Initiatives**, exploiting the experience and network of EDERA, as well as the contact portfolio of the other involved partners (Eurac Research, Instituto Valenciano De La Edificación, Nobatek and Huygen Ingenieurs & Adviseurs). According to the 3 main pillars and in support to other Infinite activities, the Observatory main functions will be:

1. managing and populating the **Online techno-economic knowledge hub** and the **Interactive market potential map** (see deliverable D7.9 and D5.3)
2. delivering an **IDR bi-annual outlook** (see chapter 4 and deliverable D7.11) able to present the most important advancements and progress in this field
3. proposing **dissemination and dedicated training activities** for the different key stakeholders in the Renovation4.0 value-chain (see deliverable D7.8 and D7.12)
4. lobbying for **policy recommendation**.

The relationship between the above-mentioned INFINITE outputs is presented in *Figure 1*. In summary, the engaged stakeholders of the Observatory contribute to provide data on IDR projects, trends and solutions which are collected offsite in the knowledge Hub database to be, then, visualized in different format in the biannual Outlook, in the market potential map and in the online repository of the Hub Itself.

Figure 1: Relationship among the Observatory, the Online techno-economic knowledge hub, the Interactive market potential map and the IDR bi-annual outlook.

2. Process to structure the IDR Observatory

EDERA led the definition and structuring process of the Observatory through a phased engagement strategy:

- **Activation of the INFINITE Consortium Network:** project partners were mobilized to share their contact portfolios and initiate outreach at national and EU levels.
- **Digital Communication and targeted outreach:** direct communications and bilateral meetings were used to identify and connect with Interested stakeholders.
- **Sign of the letter of support:** the identified stakeholders (see chapter 3) signed a customized letter of support to the IDR Observatory in which they mention their possible contribution to the initiative (see letter template in Annex 1). All letters are collected as a means of verification of the achievement of milestone MS15 (engage a wide audience of stakeholders about the Observatory).
- **Workshops:** two dedicated workshops were held in Italy in May 2023 and November 2024 to foster dialogue around IDR approach, its benefits and current challenges. These sessions also

served as venues to gather stakeholder input and build engagement around the Observatory (see deliverable D7.12 for further insights into the workshops).

- **Online and in-presence meetings:** online meetings have been organized with most engaged stakeholders to agree on their contribution within the Observatory initiative. With some other organizations the involvement is planned for the second edition of the IDR bi-annual outlook (see chapter 4). One In-presence meeting occurred In January 2024 in Paris with all the Energiesprong Network to define an International common set of parameters needed to characterize Industrialized renovation projects and enable objective comparisons.

3. Stakeholders involved in the IDR Observatory

To ensure the **neutrality, depth, and inclusiveness** of the IDR Observatory, EDERA coordinated the engagement of a set of high-level stakeholders whose involvement goes beyond technical solution provision and supply-chain participation to deliver specific projects. These actors represent **aggregators, research hubs, industry alliances, and non-profit networks** that influence the broader ecosystem of renovation and urban transformation. As part of Milestone MS15, Letters of Support to the Observatory initiative were formally collected (see letter template in Annex 1) from the following organizations:

- **ANCE– National Association of Builders (Italy)**
ANCE is Italy’s largest construction industry association. While rooted in traditional construction, ANCE has increasingly championed renovation and sustainability agendas. Their involvement in the Observatory offers a bridge to policy makers, contractors and construction companies, helping to widespread the adoption of industrialized methods with mainstream building approaches.
- **Buildwise (Belgium)**
Buildwise (formerly CSTC-WTCB) is Belgium’s leading construction technology research institute, serving the entire building sector through applied R&D, technical guidance, and innovation dissemination. With deep expertise in construction systems, Buildwise contributes to the Observatory by sharing technical benchmarking, standardization insights, and supporting the integration of industrialized solutions into Belgian current practices.
- **CRESME (Italy)**
CRESME is a strategic research center focused on construction market intelligence and socio-economic analysis in Italy. Their participation strengthens the Observatory’s analytical backbone, providing forecasts, cost-benefit evaluations, and macroeconomic data to support Renovation4.0 uptake, especially for the second edition of the IDR Outlook.
- **Energiesprong Global Alliance and National Market Development Teams (Ressorts, Energiesprong UK, DENA, Depact)**
Energiesprong is a Dutch-born initiative now operating across multiple European countries, pioneering the performance-based offsite retrofit model. Rather than offering specific technologies, they coordinate market development by aligning housing providers, industry,

and policymakers to create scalable IDR demand. Their role in the Observatory is pivotal in sharing scalable business cases and performance monitoring standards.

- **FHS - Fondazione Housing Sociale (Italy)**
FHS is a non-profit foundation advancing affordable housing models with a focus on social inclusion and sustainability. It acts as a lab for public-private partnerships in urban regeneration. Through the Observatory, FHS supports the development of IDR strategies that are inclusive, affordable, and replicable.
- **Hors Site (France)**
Hors Site is a French think tank and editorial platform dedicated to promoting offsite and industrialized construction methods. By documenting and communicating innovations in prefabrication and modularity, Hors Site brings visibility to emerging solutions. Their involvement ensures the Observatory benefits from cutting-edge industrial trends and narratives, contributing to its content dissemination role.
- **Housing Europe (EU)**
As the European federation of public, cooperative and social housing providers, Housing Europe brings the voice of over 43,000 housing providers to the table. Their engagement ensures the Observatory is aligned with real-world needs, capable of scaling IDR across millions of homes and reflecting tenants' needs.
- **Modular Building Institute (MBI)**
The MBI is a global non-profit trade association representing the modular construction industry, especially active in North America and Europe. Their participation provides international benchmarking and strategic foresight on modular approaches, regulations, and business models. MBI supports the Observatory in identifying cross-continental best practices in industrialized retrofitting.
- **REbuild (Italy)**
REbuild is a national platform for innovation in the built environment in Italy. It promotes the digital and industrial transformation of the construction sector, acting as a knowledge accelerator and networking hub. REbuild is particularly focused on industrialized processes, so it can contribute to the Observatory, by disseminating Renovation4.0 approaches through national conferences, sector dialogues and policy recommendations.
- **Renowave (Austria)**
Renowave is a national innovation platform for building renovation and sustainability. It connects diverse players across the construction, finance, and research sectors in Austria. Their contribution focuses on system-level insights, policy dialogue, and creating bridges between market readiness and national climate strategies. They support the Observatory in gathering structured innovation data and Austrian best practices.

As said, these stakeholders form a multi-disciplinary consortium, deliberately selected for their **neutrality and ecosystem-level insights**. Their ongoing participation ensures that the Observatory is not just a passive knowledge hub, but a **living platform for collective innovation, evidence-building, and market activation**.

4. Contribution to bi-annual IDR outlook

The Observatory's stakeholders have mainly contributed to the first edition of the **bi-annual IDR outlook** or will contribute to its second edition planned for January 2026.

The main activities carried out - especially by the Energiesprong network in the meeting in Paris - were:

- the **definition and validation of a common framework and benchmark** (with relevant KPIs) to be shared to INFINITE project partners and external entities to collect information about their best national IDR practices.
- **compilation of the framework with homogenous projects' information** able to collect IDR best practices (see deliverable D7.11, final session on case studies).

The output is a projects' list where all the indicators are placed in different columns that can be properly filtered, according to specific categories (general, building, retrofit, economic, performances).

Overall, the **first edition of the IDR Outlook** covered:

- the regulatory framework and the objectives that Europe has set to achieve a rapid and effective decarbonization process;
- current environmental, economic and social challenges that the construction sector is facing;
- the meaning of Industrialized Deep Renovation (IDR), focusing on the benefits that this new approach can bring compared to traditional interventions;
- the best practices in the field of research and development, such as the European LIFE and Horizon projects;
- the experience and peculiarities of the international Energiesprong movement in the different national contexts;
- presentation of pilot projects (with a table reporting the parameters defined by the common framework) carried out in Germany, France, the United Kingdom, the Netherlands, Slovenia and Italy.

For the upcoming second edition, the focus will be on:

- Quantitative analysis showcasing market potential of Industrialized solutions
- Techno-economic trends and benefits (mainly focused on cost and time reductions)
- Testimonials and interviews with technological leaders and frontrunners
- Success cases demonstrating the replicability and scalability of the IDR approach.

Since this new version will include more market-oriented and cost-related data, a "**stealth participation mode**" might be planned to collect more sensitive information.

5. Current limitations and future perspectives

The IDR Observatory has successfully launched a foundational structure, engaged a neutral and knowledgeable group of actors, and contributed to techno-economic dissemination via the first IDR Outlook. However, several challenges remain:

- **Maintenance:** ensuring continuous data inflow and platform updates post-project duration.
- **Inclusiveness:** broadening participation beyond initial actors to include more entities, representing a broader range of national contexts.
- **Recognition:** establishing the Observatory as a go-to reference point for IDR knowledge and policy support.

Future efforts will focus on **expanding the network** thanks to the presentation and dissemination of the first IDR Outlook and the online publication of the Tecno-Economic knowledge Hub. Indeed, the Observatory has the potential to become a **flagship initiative for scaling industrialized renovation across Europe**.

Annex

The template of the Letter of Support that has been shared and signed by all the stakeholders listed in chapter 3 is presented below.

To: EDERA s.r.l. Impresa Sociale
V. Ambrogio Bergognone da Fossano, 34
20144 Milano MI

Letter of support

Dear Thomas Miorin,

I am pleased to confirm the interest and support of **[Name of the organization]** in joining the initiative "**The Industrialized Deep Retrofit (IDR) Observatory**", part of the Horizon 2020 INFINITE project, that promotes a new model for deep renovation of residential buildings, leveraging digitalisation and industrialised prefabrication to deliver faster, more cost-effective, and environmentally sustainable solutions.

Within this context, the IDR Observatory serves as a stakeholder-driven platform that fosters knowledge exchange and engagement to support the adoption of the Renovation4.0 approach across Europe.

[Name of the organization], operating in the field of **[insert area of activity]**, is supporting the objective and the activities of the IDR Observatory.

Through **[insert form of support/contribution]**, the organization will provide expertise, knowledge, and resources aligned with the aims of the INFINITE initiative.

Looking forward to a successful cooperation.

Organisation **Insert here**
Name **Insert here**
Title **Insert here**
Signature

Date **Insert here**

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